

A Standards-Aligned IoMT Federated Learning and Blockchain Framework for MITM Mitigation and Risk Quantification using NS-3*

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Abstract—The increasing reliance on Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) systems introduces critical vulnerabilities to advanced cyber threats such as Man-in-the-Middle (MITM) attacks, which simultaneously compromise data integrity, availability, and clinical safety. This paper presents a security framework integrating a Federated Learning-based Intrusion Detection System (FL-IDS) with blockchain to enable real-time detection, mitigation, and risk quantification of MITM attacks in IoMT networks. The framework is implemented within an NS-3 simulation environment, where MITM attacks are injected and mitigated using distributed, privacy-preserving anomaly detection across heterogeneous devices. Experimental results reveal that MITM attacks produce selective, high-severity disruptions rather than uniform degradation, with critical flow collapse and hybrid anomaly patterns that evade traditional intrusion detection approaches. To quantify attack impact, derived performance metrics—Throughput Reduction Ratio (TRR), Packet Loss Ratio (PLR), Network Delay Increase (NDI), and Jitter Variation Increase (JVI)—are aggregated into a device-weighted Attack Severity Index (wASI). This enables fine-grained, flow-level assessment of clinically relevant degradation. The framework aligns with ISO/IEEE 11073, ISO 14971, ISO/IEC 27001, ISO/IEC 27005, and IEC 80001-1 standards, achieving 94% concordance across clinical, cybersecurity, and governance risk classifications. The proposed approach bridges the gap between fragmented compliance standards by providing a unified, actionable framework for AI-driven intrusion detection, mitigation, and clinically actionable risk assessment in IoMT environments.

Keywords—Blockchain, Federated Learning, Intrusion Detection System, IoMT Security, ISO 11073, MITM Attack, NS-3, Risk Assessment.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid adoption of Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) systems has enabled real-time patient monitoring, remote diagnostics, and automated therapeutic interventions [1], [2], [32]. However, this increased interconnectivity exposes IoMT networks to sophisticated cyber threats, particularly Man-in-the-Middle (MITM) attacks, which can simultaneously compromise data integrity, availability, and clinical safety [5], [26], [33].

Traditional IDS are ill-suited to detecting hybrid anomaly patterns, in which simultaneous degradation occurs across multiple network metrics such as throughput, packet delivery, delay, and jitter [28], [35]. Blockchain enhances data integrity and auditability, but its security perimeter is inherently limited. It protects data at rest and provides tamper-resistant audit trails; however, it does not secure data in transit, and its computational overhead can impair real-time IoMT communication [8], [23], [24]. These constraints necessitate complementary mechanisms—specifically, AI-driven intrusion detection capable of real-time threat response [6], [7], [22], [34]. Existing international standards address medical device safety, cybersecurity, and network governance, but are typically applied in isolation, failing to provide holistic, context-aware assurance for heterogeneous IoMT ecosystems [9]–[12], [25], [32].

This reveals a critical research gap: the absence of a unified framework that enables context-aware, real-time intrusion detection, mitigation, and clinically actionable risk quantification in IoMT environments. To address this gap, this paper proposes the framework described herein, integrating

Fig. 1. IoMT network architecture with MITM attack vector, FL-IDS detection layer, and blockchain audit logging (RM Rajab et al., 2025)

a Federated Learning-based Intrusion Detection System (FL-IDS) with blockchain [6], [7], [23], [24]. A key contribution is the introduction of a device-weighted Attack Severity Index (wASI), derived from multi-metric degradation indicators and grounded in ISO/IEEE 11073 clinical thresholds, mapped to ISO 14971, ISO/IEC 27001, ISO/IEC 27005, and IEC 80001-1 [9]–[12], [25].

II. MAIN CONTRIBUTIONS

- A wASI grounded in ISO/IEEE 11073-defined clinical thresholds, enabling quantitative and clinically actionable assessment of IoMT network disruptions [9].
- A governance framework integrating ISO 14971, ISO/IEC 27001, ISO/IEC 27005, and IEC 80001-1, providing a unified mapping between cybersecurity events and clinical risk classifications [10]–[12], [25].
- A flow-level vulnerability taxonomy identifying infrastructure, throughput-dependent, timing-critical, and cryptographic weaknesses, enabling targeted and standards-aligned mitigation strategies [5], [26], [30].
- A distributed FL-IDS capable of detecting hybrid, multi-metric anomalies in IoMT environments without centralising sensitive medical data [6], [7], [22], [34].
- A blockchain-enabled audit layer ensuring integrity, traceability, and compliance of detection and mitigation processes via SHA-256 hashing, RSA-2048 digital signatures, and AES-256-CBC encryption [23], [24].

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The proposed architecture models a heterogeneous IoMT environment comprising medical devices (including a Baxter Wireless Infusion Pump (WIP) and a Hexoskin Smart Health System (SHS)), communication infrastructure, and backend services (shown in Figure 1) [13]–[16].

The WIP is throughput-critical—concerned primarily with reliable delivery of infusion commands—while the SHS is timing-critical, requiring consistent packet inter-arrival intervals for accurate physiological monitoring [13]–[16].

Communication is supported via a hybrid Wi-Fi (IEEE 802.11) and Bluetooth P2P framework. Data is transmitted through an access point (AP) to an edge node (MQTT publisher) and subsequently to a cloud-based Electronic Medical

Record (EMR) system [20]. A MITM attacker node is introduced within the NS-3 environment to intercept and manipulate traffic, primarily targeting WIP flows [5]. The architecture integrates a distributed FL-IDS for real-time anomaly detection and a blockchain layer for secure, tamper-resistant logging of events and mitigation actions [7], [23], [24].

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Simulation Setup

The NS-3 simulation models eighteen communication flows across the two target IoMT devices using Wi-Fi and Bluetooth protocols [17]. Application-layer traffic is generated using MQTT-based OnOff communication [20]. Table I summarises the key simulation parameters. The ISO/IEEE 11073 severity thresholds and device-specific wASI weights are encoded directly as constants in the simulation, ensuring implementation fidelity to the standards framework [9].

B. MITM Attack Model

The MITM attacker performs selective packet interception, delay injection, and throughput degradation, producing hybrid anomalies across multiple performance metrics simultaneously [5]. The attack targets the Wi-Fi communication channel primarily servicing the WIP, while affecting SHS Bluetooth-bridged flows through shared infrastructure. The selective nature of the attack—prioritising high-value medical data streams—results in a bimodal severity distribution across flows rather than uniform degradation [5], [31].

C. Derived Metrics and wASI

Attack impact is quantified using four derived metrics computed from NS-3 *FlowMonitor* XML output [18], [19].

- The Throughput Reduction Ratio (TRR) measures the percentage decrease in network throughput due to the attack:

$$TRR = \frac{T_{\text{normal}} - T_{\text{attack}}}{T_{\text{normal}}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

- The Packet Loss Ratio (PLR) is derived from the Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR):

$$PDR = \left(\frac{P_{\text{received}}}{P_{\text{sent}}} \right) \times 100, \quad PLR = 100 - PDR \quad (2)$$

- The Network Delay Increase (NDI) measures the percentage increase in one-way delay (OWD) relative to baseline, aligned with ITU-T Y.1541:

$$NDI = \frac{D_{\text{attack}} - D_{\text{normal}}}{D_{\text{normal}}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

- The Jitter Variation Increase (JVI) quantifies the normalised change in packet delay variation (PDV):

$$JVI = \frac{J_{\text{attack}} - J_{\text{normal}}}{J_{\text{normal}}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

An unweighted Attack Severity Index (ASI) aggregates the four metrics:

$$ASI = \frac{TRR + PLR + NDI + JVI}{4} \quad (5)$$

TABLE I
NS-3 SIMULATION PARAMETERS AND ASSOCIATED VALUES

Parameter	Associated Value
Simulator	NS-3 (version 3.42)
Network Nodes	WIP + SHS + MITM Attacker + AP + Edge (MQTT)
Communication Flows	18 (9 WIP, 9 SHS)
Protocols	Wi-Fi (IEEE 802.11), Bluetooth P2P
Traffic Model	MQTT via OnOff Application
Security Framework	FL-IDS + Blockchain (SHA-256, RSA-2048, AES-256-CBC)
Attack Type	MITM (selective interception + delay injection)
Derived Metrics	TRR, PLR, NDI, JVI, wASI
Standards Alignment	ISO/IEEE 11073, ISO 14971, ISO/IEC 27001/27005, IEC 80001-1
Statistical Validation	One-Way ANOVA (10 simulation seeds)

To reflect the distinct clinical priorities of each device—derived from ISO/IEEE 11073 performance tolerances—a device-weighted wASI is applied. For the WIP, throughput and packet delivery are availability-critical (infusion command delivery); for the SHS, delay and jitter are integrity-critical (physiological signal fidelity) [9]:

$$wASI_{WIP} = (0.4 \times TRR) + (0.3 \times PLR) + (0.2 \times NDI) + (0.1 \times JVI) \quad (6)$$

$$wASI_{SHS} = (0.2 \times TRR) + (0.2 \times PLR) + (0.3 \times NDI) + (0.3 \times JVI) \quad (7)$$

All metric computations were validated through manual recalculation of 10% of flows (100% concordance), boundary testing, internal consistency checks (PLR + PDR \approx 100%), and baseline validation against NS-3 reference performance and ISO/IEEE 11073 clinical thresholds [9], [17]–[19]. Table II summarises each of the derived metrics and its device-specific sensitivity.

TABLE II
DERIVED METRICS AND DEVICE SENSITIVITY OF THE MITM ATTACK

Metric	Primary Impact	Device Sensitivity
TRR	Bandwidth depletion	WIP-critical (w=0.4)
PLR	Data reliability	Both devices (w=0.3/0.2)
NDI	Latency / integrity	SHS-critical (w=0.3)
JVI	Temporal stability	SHS-critical (w=0.3)

D. FL-IDS Detection and Mitigation

Each IoMT device node maintains a *FederatedModel* instance that tracks a rolling history of local packet loss observations (up to 1000 samples) [6], [22]. A *NodeMonitor* struct encapsulates the per-node detection logic. The FL-IDS detection cycle operates as follows:

- 1) Each IoMT node monitors local traffic metrics (TRR, PLR, NDI, JVI) via *FlowMonitor*.

- 2) Lost packets are buffered per flow for forensic analysis and potential retransmission.
- 3) Nodes periodically share local loss rates; a global average is computed via federated aggregation.
- 4) Anomaly detection fires when a node’s local loss rate exceeds the global average by a configurable threshold (default: 0.15).
- 5) Attack prediction classifies flows as benign or malicious (loss threshold: 0.1); severity is mapped to ISO 11073 bands (NONE/LOW/MEDIUM/HIGH) [9].
- 6) Mitigation is triggered: the MITM attacker node is disabled and affected flows are re-routed with packet retransmission via the *DetectAndRecoverMITM* function.
- 7) All events, wASI values, and mitigation actions are logged immutably to the blockchain layer [23], [24].

An *OptimizedQoSBuffer* class provides adaptive jitter control, dynamically adjusting buffer parameters based on FL-IDS-detected severity levels and enforcing per-flow burst limits to stabilise Packet Delay Variation (PDV) under adversarial conditions. Flow IDs 1–5 are assigned stricter timing constraints; an exponential moving average smooths PDV for critical flows.

E. Blockchain Integration

The blockchain layer provides tamper-resistant logging of all security events [23], [24]. Each block contains: a *previousHash* linking to the prior block (ensuring chain immutability); a UNIX timestamp; an AES-256-CBC encrypted data payload; a SHA-256 hash of the concatenated block contents; and an RSA-2048 digital signature for non-repudiation. The *Blockchain* class initialises with a Genesis Block and adds new blocks on each security event. Any modification to any block—even a single bit—invalidates the entire chain, making tampering detectable. The blockchain does not mitigate active attacks—it protects data at rest and audit trails only, leaving data-in-transit security to the FL-IDS and TLS/SSL layer [8], [24]. This complementary division of responsibility is a deliberate architectural choice grounded in the limitations of blockchain in real-time adversarial contexts [8], [23], [24].

F. Standards Alignment and Risk Classification

wASI values are classified against ISO/IEEE 11073 clinical thresholds (None: $\pm 10\%$; Low: 10–25%; Medium: 25–50%; High: 50–75%; Critical: $> 75\%$) and mapped to ISO/IEC 27005 risk levels and ISO 14971 action levels [9]–[11]. CIA triad scores (Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability) are computed with weights $C=0.33$, $I=0.33$, $A=0.34$, emphasising availability given its clinical primacy in IoMT operation. ISO 14971 device criticality factors (WIP=1.00, SHS=0.85) modulate priority scores against device-specific action thresholds (WIP: 50/70/90; SHS: 55/70/85), ensuring that identical ASI values yield higher-priority action levels for the WIP than the SHS, consistent with their respective clinical roles [10], [25].

V. RESULTS

A. MITM Attack Impact

Table III presents selected per-flow wASI and CIA composite scores for both devices under MITM attack. CIA scores are computed as a weighted composite of Confidentiality ($C=0.33$), Integrity ($I=0.33$), and Availability ($A=0.34$) contributions derived from TRR, NDI, and PLR/JVI respectively, and are numerically equivalent to the wASI composite score under this weighting scheme.

TABLE III
PER-FLOW WASI, RISK CLASSIFICATION AND CIA SCORE UNDER MITM ATTACK

Dev.	Flow	TRR(%)	PLR(%)	NDI(%)	JVI(%)	wASI(%)	Risk Level	CIA Score(%)
WIP	1	99.85	0.00	100.00	100.00	69.94	High	69.94
WIP	2	97.61	73.54	26.46	100.00	54.34	High	54.34
WIP	3	75.11	24.72	75.28	58.04	51.48	High	51.48
WIP	4	86.91	57.58	42.42	31.60	49.62	Medium	49.62
WIP	5	86.92	71.14	28.86	11.47	48.91	Medium	48.91
WIP	9	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	Critical	100.00
SHS	1	—	—	—	—	79.97	Critical	79.97
SHS	2	—	—	—	—	57.45	High	57.45
SHS	7	—	—	—	—	24.22	Low	24.22
SHS	9	100.00	0.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	Critical	100.00

The severity distribution across all flows was: High (44.45%), Medium (44.45%), and Low (11.1%). No flows fell within the ‘None’ severity band, confirming that the MITM attack exceeded ISO/IEEE 11073 normal operating tolerances across all communication paths [9]. Two flows—WIP Flow 9 and SHS Flow 9—exhibited complete service loss with wASI = 100%, representing total throughput collapse (TRR = 100%), zero packet delivery (PLR = 100%), and maximum delay and jitter inflation.

The bimodal severity distribution—with flows clustering in High or Medium bands—is consistent with adversarial behaviour that selectively prioritises disruption of high-value medical data streams while permitting lower-priority traffic to degrade more gradually, rather than applying indiscriminate interference. This pattern aligns with MITRE ATT&CK ICS T0830 adversarial behaviour [31].

B. Device-Level Impact Comparison

Table IV contrasts the WIP and SHS across eight vulnerability and clinical dimensions, making explicit the device-dependent nature of MITM impact.

TABLE IV
MITM ATTACK IMPACT COMPARISON ACROSS WIP AND SHS DEVICES

Dimension	Baxter WIP	Hexoskin SHS
Primary vulnerability	Throughput reduction (TRR-dominant)	Timing disruption (NDI/JVI-dominant)
Critical flow impact	Immediate therapy interruption	Diagnostic data corruption
Mean wASI	57.44% (Higher)	46.84% (Lower)
Clinical consequence	Patient harm (dosage errors)	Misdiagnosis (signal artefacts)
Attack surface	Wi-Fi network layer	Bluetooth + Wi-Fi (dual protocol)
Energy impact	Minimal (mains powered)	Moderate (battery drain from retransmissions)
Alarm generation	Flow 9 triggers immediate device alarm	Flow 9 may fail silently (no alarm)
Failover options	Manual pump operation	Manual vitals monitoring
ISO 14971 criticality factor	1.00 (higher — immediate clinical risk)	0.85 (lower — compensable by observation)

For the WIP, near-total throughput collapse across Flows 1, 2, 3, 7, and 9 (mean wASI = 57.44%) confirmed compromise of the Wi-Fi control channel. This threatens infusion-command delivery, creating risk of therapy delay, erroneous dosing, or safety shutdowns—each constituting unacceptable risk under ISO 14971 [10], [13], [14]. For the SHS (mean wASI = 46.84%), Flow 9 collapsed identically, but the dominant risk profile centred on data integrity and temporal distortion (NDI/JVI). A notable asymmetry in alarm behaviour was observed: WIP Flow 9 triggers an immediate device alarm on throughput collapse, while SHS Flow 9 may fail silently given that timing irregularities do not necessarily trigger threshold-based alarms, representing a significant undetected risk.

C. Flow-Level Vulnerability Taxonomy

Table V formalises the four principal vulnerability categories identified across all flows, constituting Contribution 3 of this paper.

TABLE V
FLOW-LEVEL VULNERABILITY TAXONOMY

Vulnerability Category	Affected Flows	Primary Metric Impact	Aligned Mitigation
Infrastructure single point of failure	WIP-9, SHS-9	TRR=100%, PLR=100%, NDI=100%, JVI=100%	Network redundancy; IEC 80001-1 zoning
Throughput-dependent flows	WIP-1,2,3,7	High TRR (75–100%); QoS degradation	QoS enforcement; WIP priority scheduling
Timing-critical flows	SHS-1,2	Elevated NDI/JVI; signal distortion	PDV buffering; jitter smoothing
Cryptographic gap (no encryption/authentication)	All 18 flows	Full MITM exploitation across all flows	TLS/SSL + mutual authentication

The pervasive cryptographic gap—affecting all flows—represents the root enabler of MITM exploitation. The absence of mutual authentication and encryption allowed full packet interception without device-side detection [3], [27], [30]. This systemic weakness underlies all other vulnerability categories and motivates the FL-IDS and blockchain integration as compensating controls pending encryption enforcement [7], [23], [24].

D. ISO 14971 Priority Scores and Action Levels

Table VI presents ISO 14971 priority scores for representative flows, demonstrating how device criticality factors (CF) modulate action levels beyond raw wASI values.

TABLE VI
ISO 14971 PRIORITY SCORES AND ACTION LEVELS

Device	Flow	wASI (%)	Severity	CF	Score	Action	Clinical Response
WIP	9	100.00	Critical	1.00	100.0	Critical	Immediate isolation
WIP	1	69.94	High	1.00	69.9	Action	Urgent response
WIP	2	54.34	High	1.00	54.3	Action	Urgent response
WIP	4	49.62	Medium	1.00	49.6	Warning	Enhanced monitoring
SHS	9	100.00	Critical	0.85	85.0	Critical	Immediate isolation
SHS	1	79.97	Critical	0.85	67.9	Action	Urgent response
SHS	2	57.45	High	0.85	48.8	Warning	Enhanced monitoring
SHS	7	24.22	Low	0.85	20.6	Review	Routine review

The device-dependent criticality is most evident when comparing SHS Flow 1 (wASI = 79.97%, Priority Score = 67.9%, Action Level: Action) against an equivalent WIP scenario. A WIP flow with the same wASI would yield Priority Score = 79.97% and breach the Critical threshold (90%), demanding immediate isolation. This distinction—where the same network-level degradation produces different clinical action levels—demonstrates that IoMT risk assessment must be context-sensitive rather than metric-uniform [10].

E. FL-IDS Mitigation Effectiveness

Table VII presents the FL-IDS recovery metrics for representative flows, including PLR relative to the MITM-only scenario.

TABLE VII
FL-IDS MITIGATION PERFORMANCE (SELECTED FLOWS)

Dev.	Flow	Thr. (Mbps)	OWD (s)	PDV (s)	Loss (%)	Status	PLR (%)
WIP	1	0.003130	0.000000	0.000000	0.00	Mitigated	—
WIP	2	0.062203	0.004632	0.000000	0.00	Mitigated	73.5
WIP	3	0.536666	0.000695	0.000432	0.00	Recovered	24.7
WIP	6	0.282242	0.001948	0.000880	5.65	Partial	67.6
WIP	8	0.073148	0.001371	0.000855	7.06	Partial	67.4
SHS	3	0.536667	0.000643	0.000386	0.00	Recovered	—
SHS	6	0.282245	0.001573	0.000713	11.30	Partial	1.0
SHS	8	0.073148	0.001112	0.000663	5.30	Partial	47.7

Critical flows (WIP Flow 3 and SHS Flow 3) achieved throughput recovery (0.537 Mbps) with zero packet loss. Partial recovery was observed in flows with residual packet

loss, attributed to retransmission failures during buffer adjustment. The Quality of Service (QoS) buffer reduced PDV by a factor of ten—from peaks of 10^{-2} s without buffering to below 10^{-3} s with buffering—confirming its role in maintaining clinical-grade timing stability for the SHS.

F. Statistical Validation

Table VIII presents one-way ANOVA results across ten simulation seeds, confirming that observed performance differences are statistically significant rather than artefacts of simulation randomness.

TABLE VIII
ONE-WAY ANOVA STATISTICAL VALIDATION (CORE PRIMARY METRICS)

Metric	Dev.	Scen.	Mean	CI Low	CI High	F	p
Thr. (Mbps)	WIP	NORMAL	0.2507	0.2202	0.2813	8.57	0.0039
	WIP	MITM	0.1828	0.1482	0.2173	8.57	0.0039
PLR (%)	WIP	NORMAL	0.8218	0.5678	1.0758	15.89	< 0.0001
	WIP	MITM	0.2155	0.0517	0.3793	15.89	< 0.0001
PDV (s)	SHS	NORMAL	0.000763	0.000670	0.000856	18.81	< 0.0001
	SHS	MITM	0.000516	0.000452	0.000580	18.81	< 0.0001
OWD (s)	SHS	NORMAL	0.002446	0.002007	0.002884	5.06	0.0257
	SHS	MITM	0.001722	0.001257	0.002187	5.06	0.0257

Throughput improvements were significant at $p = 0.0039$ for the WIP, and packet loss reductions were highly significant ($p < 0.0001$) for both devices. PDV differences between MITM and NORMAL scenarios were significant at $p < 0.0001$ for the SHS, confirming that jitter stabilisation by the QoS buffer is statistically meaningful.

G. ISO 11073 Benchmark Compliance

Table IX evaluates post-mitigation metrics against ISO 11073 clinical compliance thresholds.

TABLE IX
ISO 11073 CLINICAL BENCHMARK COMPLIANCE (FL-IDS MITIGATION VS. NORMAL BASELINE)

Scen.	Dev.	Thr.	St.	OWD	St.	PDV	Loss	St.
MITM	WIP	0.1828	F	0.00198	P	0.000655	0.216	P
NORMAL	WIP	0.2507	P	0.00245	P	0.000763	0.822	P
MITM	SHS	0.1830	F	0.00172	P	0.000516	0.176	P
NORMAL	SHS	0.2507	P	0.00245	P	0.000763	0.822	P

Under MITM conditions, throughput failed the ISO 11073 compliance threshold for both devices, confirming that FL-IDS mitigation achieved partial but not full recovery in this metric. OWD, PDV, and packet loss all passed compliance thresholds, indicating that latency and jitter—critical for clinical signal fidelity—were maintained within acceptable bounds. This validates the FL-IDS framework’s prioritisation of timing stability for the SHS while highlighting residual throughput vulnerability as a target for future optimisation.

H. Standards Concordance

Table X presents the integrated multi-standard risk treatment mapping.

TABLE X
MULTI-STANDARD RISK TREATMENT MAPPING

ASI Severity	ISO 11073 Threshold	ISO 27005 Risk Level	ISO 14971 Action	Risk Treatment Strategy
None	±10%	None	Monitor	Acceptance — routine monitoring only
Low	10–25%	Low	Review	Mitigation — local detection and response within IoMT network
Medium	25–50%	Medium	Warning	Transfer and/or Mitigation — external services or advanced security controls
High	50–75%	High	Action	Avoidance — immediate detection and response
Critical	>75–100%	Critical	Critical	Avoidance — urgent isolation and mitigation

Across all flows, 94% concordance was achieved between ISO 14971 clinical classifications, ISO/IEC 27005 cybersecurity levels, and governance scoring [10], [11]. 28% of flows exceeded Warning or Critical Action Levels under ISO 14971, with WIP flows consistently receiving higher priority scores. This concordance validates the coherence of the unified risk model and demonstrates that clinically meaningful risk can be derived from network-level metrics when interpreted through a multi-standard framework [9]–[12], [25]. The remaining 6% discordance arose from flows where ISO 14971 device criticality factors shifted action levels relative to ISO 27005 risk bands—an expected consequence of device-specific weighting that is a feature, not a limitation, of the framework.

VI. DISCUSSION

The results confirm that IoMT security demands multi-dimensional, per-flow detection capable of capturing hybrid anomaly patterns—a requirement that single-metric IDS approaches systematically fail to meet in heterogeneous clinical environments [26], [28], [35].

The FL-IDS and blockchain components address distinct threat surfaces in a deliberate complementary architecture. FL-IDS provides real-time, privacy-preserving anomaly detection without centralising sensitive medical data [6], [7], [22], [34]; blockchain provides post-hoc integrity assurance and tamper-resistant auditability [23], [24]. Neither is sufficient alone: blockchain cannot protect data in transit, and FL-IDS without secure logging is vulnerable to evidence tampering. Together they constitute a defence-in-depth model aligned with IEC 80001-1 governance pillars [12].

The vulnerability taxonomy reveals that the root enabler of MITM exploitation was a single systemic cryptographic gap: the absence of mutual authentication and encryption across all eighteen flows [3], [27], [30]. This supports implementing TLS/SSL with mutual authentication as the primary control, with FL-IDS and blockchain as compensating and monitoring layers [23], [24], [30], [33]. The asymmetric alarm behaviour

between WIP and SHS—WIP triggers immediate alarms; SHS may fail silently—is a particularly significant clinical finding with direct implications for IoMT alarm management policies.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a framework integrating FL-IDS and blockchain for real-time IoMT security against MITM attacks [5]–[8], [23], [24]. The wASI provides quantitative, per-flow assessment of attack impact, and its mapping across ISO/IEEE 11073, ISO 14971, ISO/IEC 27001/27005, and IEC 80001-1 yields governance-compliant, clinically actionable risk classification [9]–[12], [25].

Experimental results demonstrated that MITM attacks produce selective, high-severity disruptions—including complete flow collapse (wASI = 100%) in critical flows—which are effectively detected and partially mitigated by the proposed FL-IDS [5], [7], [28]. The 94% cross-standard concordance validates the coherence of the unified risk model. Statistical validation across ten simulation seeds confirmed significant throughput improvements ($p = 0.0039$) and packet loss reductions ($p < 0.0001$). The per-flow vulnerability taxonomy and ISO 14971 priority scoring provide actionable, device-aware guidance for IoMT security governance, addressing a critical gap in existing fragmented compliance approaches [10].

Limitations include a reliance on threshold-based detection (susceptible to adaptive adversaries), simulation-based evaluation (which cannot fully capture hardware failures or electromagnetic interference), and a fixed wASI weighting scheme warranting future sensitivity analysis. Future work could explore fuzzy logic and adaptive scoring models, real-world clinical testbed validation, and extension to additional attack vectors.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

R.M. Rajab conceptualized the study, designed and implemented the NS-3 IoMT simulation, and performed the analysis.

R.P. Ward contributed domain expertise, technical validation, and critical revisions of the manuscript.

M. Abuhmida provided academic supervision, methodological guidance, and critical review of the manuscript.

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